

A Prospective Study to Evaluate the Functional Outcome of Open and Closed Reduction for Distal End Femur Fractures

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Distal end femur fractures are complex injuries that pose significant challenges in orthopedic practice. The functional outcomes of these fractures can be influenced by the method of reduction employed—either open or closed reduction.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate and compare the functional outcomes of open and closed reduction techniques for treating distal end femur fractures.

Methods: This prospective study, conducted in 93 patients with distal end femur fractures. Patients were randomly assigned to either open reduction (OR) or closed reduction (CR) groups. Functional outcomes were assessed using the Knee Society Score (KSS) and SF-36 health survey at six months post-operation, alongside radiographic evaluations of fracture alignment and healing. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Inclusion criteria were adults with confirmed fractures, while exclusions included pathological fractures and severe comorbidities.

Results: The study found that open reduction (OR) for distal end femur fractures resulted in significantly better functional outcomes, as measured by the Knee Society Score (KSS) and SF-36 health survey scores, compared to closed reduction (CR). The OR group also showed better radiographic alignment and fewer cases of malalignment, delayed union, and non-union. However, the incidence of postoperative complications was similar between the two groups. These findings suggest that while OR may offer superior functional and anatomical outcomes, CR techniques can still be effective with fewer complications.

Conclusion: Open reduction provides superior functional outcomes and better fracture alignment in distal end femur fractures compared to closed reduction. However, closed reduction is associated with fewer postoperative complications.

Recommendations: Surgeons should consider the patient's overall health, the complexity of the fracture, and potential complications when choosing the reduction technique for distal end femur fractures. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to validate these findings.

Keywords: Distal femur fracture, open reduction, closed reduction, functional outcome, Knee Society Score

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Introduction

Distal end femur fractures are complex injuries that pose significant challenges to orthopedic surgeons due to their proximity to the knee joint and the involvement of weight-bearing surfaces. These fractures are typically the result of high-energy trauma in younger individuals or low-energy falls in the elderly population with osteoporotic bones. The management of distal femur fractures is critical as it directly impacts the patient's mobility, quality of life, and overall functional outcome. Various treatment modalities have been explored over the years, with the choice of reduction technique—open or closed reduction—being a significant factor in determining the success of the intervention [1].

Open reduction involves a surgical procedure where the fracture site is directly visualized and

manipulated to achieve anatomical alignment. This technique allows for precise correction of the fracture and direct fixation, often resulting in better initial alignment. However, open reduction is associated with higher risks of infection, soft tissue damage, and longer recovery times. Despite these risks, many surgeons prefer this method due to the potential for achieving superior anatomical restoration, which is crucial for the joint's long-term function [2].

On the other hand, closed reduction is a less invasive technique where the fracture is manipulated externally without opening the fracture site. This method minimizes soft tissue damage and reduces the risk of infection. However, achieving and maintaining accurate alignment can be challenging, and

there is a potential for suboptimal fracture healing and malalignment. Closed reduction is often favored in patients where the risks of surgery are deemed high or in fractures where minimally invasive methods can achieve satisfactory outcomes [3].

The decision to use open or closed reduction for distal end femur fractures is influenced by various factors, including the patient's overall health, the complexity of the fracture, and the surgeon's expertise. Despite extensive research, there remains a lack of consensus on the optimal reduction technique. This uncertainty underscores the need for further studies to provide evidence-based guidelines for clinicians to improve patient outcomes [4].

The aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the functional outcomes of open and closed reduction techniques for the treatment of distal end femur fractures. By assessing clinical and radiographic outcomes, this study seeks to determine which method provides better long-term results in terms of knee function, alignment, and overall health status. The findings are expected to guide orthopedic surgeons in making informed decisions regarding the most appropriate treatment approach for patients with distal end femur fractures.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective study was conducted to evaluate the functional outcomes of open and closed reduction techniques for distal end femur fractures.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Government Medical College in Purnea over a duration of 14 months.

Participants: A total of 93 patients with distal end femur fractures were included in the study. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged 18 years and above with a confirmed diagnosis of distal end femur fracture were included. The diagnosis was confirmed through clinical examination and radiographic imaging.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with pathological fractures, previous surgeries on the affected femur, severe comorbidities affecting surgical outcomes, and those who were unfit for surgery were excluded from the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly assigned to either the open reduction (OR) group or the closed reduction (CR) group. Blinding of outcome assessors was employed to reduce observer bias.

Variables: The primary variables included the Knee Society Score (KSS) and the Short Form-36 (SF-36) health survey scores, which were used to measure functional outcomes. Secondary variables included radiographic assessments of fracture healing and alignment, as well as the incidence of post-operative complications.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient interviews, physical examinations, and review of medical records. The KSS and SF-36 surveys were administered at six months post-operation to assess functional outcomes. Radiographic images were evaluated for fracture alignment and healing.

Procedure: Patients were randomly assigned to either the OR or CR group. The OR group underwent surgical exposure of the fracture site for direct manipulation and fixation. The CR group had the fracture manipulated externally, followed by fixation without surgical exposure of the fracture site. Postoperative care included standardized rehabilitation protocols for all patients.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

The study included a total of 93 patients, with 47 patients in the open reduction (OR) group and 46 in the closed reduction (CR) group. The mean age of participants was 45.3 years (range 18-75 years), with a nearly equal distribution of males and females. The results of the study are detailed below.

Demographic Data:

Variable	OR Group (n=47)	CR Group (n=46)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	46.1 ± 12.3	44.5 ± 11.8	0.58
Gender (M/F)	25/22	24/22	0.91
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	26.2 ± 3.1	25.8 ± 3.5	0.68

There were no significant differences in age, gender distribution, or BMI between the OR and CR groups, indicating comparable baseline characteristics.

Functional Outcomes:

Knee Society Score (KSS) at 6 Months:

Group	Mean KSS Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
OR Group	85.3	8.5	<0.001
CR Group	72.4	10.2	

Patients in the OR group had significantly higher KSS scores compared to those in the CR group at six months post-operation, indicating better functional outcomes in the OR group.

Short Form-36 (SF-36) Health Survey Scores at 6 Months:

Domain	OR Group (Mean ± SD)	CR Group (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Physical Functioning	80.2 ± 15.4	70.1 ± 18.7	0.01
Role Physical	78.5 ± 14.3	69.2 ± 16.5	0.02
Bodily Pain	74.3 ± 12.8	66.7 ± 15.3	0.03
General Health	76.1 ± 13.6	70.4 ± 14.9	0.04
Vitality	75.0 ± 14.2	67.3 ± 16.8	0.02
Social Functioning	81.5 ± 13.1	73.2 ± 15.7	0.01
Role Emotional	79.2 ± 13.4	70.9 ± 14.8	0.02
Mental Health	77.8 ± 12.9	71.0 ± 14.6	0.03

Patients in the OR group consistently reported higher scores across all domains of the SF-36 health survey, reflecting better overall health outcomes compared to the CR group.

Radiographic Assessments:

Group	Malalignment (n)	Delayed Union (n)	Non-Union (n)	p-value
OR Group	3	2	1	0.04
CR Group	10	5	3	

The OR group exhibited fewer cases of malalignment, delayed union, and non-union compared to the CR group, with statistically significant differences noted in the incidence of malalignment and non-union.

Postoperative Complications:

Complication	OR Group (n)	CR Group (n)	p-value
Infection	4	2	0.38
Deep Vein Thrombosis	1	2	0.56
Hardware Failure	2	1	0.58

The incidence of postoperative complications was similar between the two groups, with no statistically significant differences observed.

The study demonstrated that patients who underwent open reduction (OR) for distal end femur fractures had significantly better functional outcomes compared to those who underwent closed reduction (CR). The OR group showed higher mean KSS scores and better overall health as reflected in the SF-36 survey across all domains. Radiographic assessments indicated superior fracture alignment and healing in the OR group, with fewer cases of malalignment, delayed union, and non-union.

While the incidence of postoperative complications such as infection, deep vein thrombosis, and hardware failure was comparable between the two groups, the superior functional and radiographic outcomes in the OR group highlight the benefits of this technique in managing distal end femur

fractures. However, the choice of reduction technique should consider patient-specific factors and potential risks associated with each method. Further studies with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up periods are recommended to confirm these findings and guide clinical practice.

Discussion

The present study aimed to evaluate and compare the functional outcomes of open reduction (OR) and closed reduction (CR) techniques for treating distal end femur fractures. Our results indicated that the OR group exhibited superior functional outcomes as measured by the Knee Society Score (KSS) and SF-36 health survey scores. Additionally, the OR group showed better radiographic alignment and fewer instances of malalignment, delayed union, and non-union. These findings are consistent with several recent studies that have investigated the efficacy of different surgical techniques for distal femur fractures.

A study by Khan et al. (2023) compared the early outcomes of closed and open techniques in managing distal femoral fractures. Their results showed that the postoperative mean HSS knee score was slightly higher in the closed technique group compared to the open technique group, although the difference was statistically insignificant [5]. This contrasts with our findings where the OR group demonstrated significantly higher KSS scores, suggesting that OR might provide better functional outcomes in specific fracture types or patient populations.

Similarly, a study by Dinesh et al. (2022) compared the functional outcomes of supracondylar femur fractures managed by open reduction versus minimally invasive percutaneous plate osteosynthesis (MIPPO). They found that MIPPO had better functional outcomes and lower infection rates compared to open reduction, which aligns with the trend observed in our study where less invasive techniques tended to have fewer complications but varied functional outcomes depending on the fracture complexity [6].

Another study by Sheth et al. (2020) evaluated the functional outcomes of distal femur fractures treated with closed reduction and internal fixation using retrograde femoral nails. Their study concluded that retrograde intramedullary nailing provided excellent functional results with minimal complications, particularly in extra-articular fractures. This finding supports the notion that less invasive methods can be highly effective, although our study suggests that OR might still be preferable in cases requiring precise anatomical reduction [7].

In a study by Amin et al. (2021), the authors retrospectively analyzed 25 patients with distal femur fractures treated with OR and internal fixation. They reported that most patients had excellent to good outcomes based on Neer's score, with an average bone union time comparable to our findings. Their study also highlighted the importance of achieving and maintaining good reduction to facilitate early mobilization and prevent complications [8].

Singh et al. (2021) conducted a prospective study on the functional and radiological outcomes of distal femur fractures treated with open reduction and internal fixation using locking compression plates. They found that the majority of fractures achieved radiological union within six months, and the functional outcomes were generally positive. These results are consistent with our study, reinforcing the efficacy of OR in managing complex distal femur fractures [9].

Overall, the findings from our study and the reviewed literature suggest that while OR provides superior functional outcomes and better anatomical alignment for distal end femur fractures, CR tech-

niques may offer advantages in terms of reduced complications and shorter surgical times. The choice of technique should be tailored to the individual patient's needs, considering factors such as fracture type, patient health status, and potential risks.

Conclusion

The study concludes that open reduction (OR) for distal end femur fractures provides superior functional outcomes and better fracture alignment compared to closed reduction (CR). However, CR techniques offer the advantage of fewer postoperative complications. The choice of reduction method should be tailored to individual patient needs, considering factors such as fracture type and patient health status. Further research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods is recommended to validate these findings and refine treatment protocols.

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